

Critical appraisal of the economic evidence for a watch-and-wait strategy in people with clinical complete response following neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy for rectal cancer: a systematic review

Citation

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Review question

How many published studies have reported an economic evaluation of a watch-and-wait strategy in people with clinical complete response following neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy for rectal cancer?

What are the economic evidence for watch-and-wait strategy in these identified published studies?

Searches

MEDLINE and Embase, both via Ovid, no date restriction, English language only

Types of study to be included

Decision-analytic model-based study and prospective study undertaking full economic evaluation ((cost-effectiveness analysis, cost-utility analysis, cost-benefit analysis). Any study which is not full economic evaluation will not be included in the review. Only studies published in journals will be included and abstracts, dissertation and unpublished studies will be excluded.

Condition or domain being studied

Rectal cancer.

Participants/population

Adults (18 years and above) with locally advanced rectal cancer who have achieved clinical complete response following neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy will be included in this review. Adults (18 years and above) with locally advanced rectal cancer who have not achieved clinical complete response or who are near clinical complete response following neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy will be excluded from this review.

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

The intervention is watch-and-wait strategy which is defined as an active surveillance where patient with clinical complete response undergoes an intensive follow-up program of regular scans and examinations of the rectum by flexible sigmoidoscopy.

Comparator(s)/control

Only resection surgery will be included. Other procedures such as endoscopic micro-dissection surgery will be excluded.

Context [1 change]

Patients that have achieved clinical complete response can potentially avoid surgery and opt for active monitoring termed a 'watch-and-wait' strategy. The possibility of avoiding complications due to surgery and permanent stoma is appealing to the patients and this strategy is gaining popularity in practice. Evidence of the cost-effectiveness of a watch-and-wait strategy compared with alternative management options for people with clinical complete response following neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy for rectal cancer will assist in evidence-based decision making and enable decision-makers to make policy decision on whether to endorse and implement this strategy of organ preservation.

Main outcome(s) [1 change]

The main outcomes of this review are:

- The number and type of published studies reporting an economic evaluation of the watch-and-wait strategy in people with clinical complete response following neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy for rectal cancer.
- Summary of the methodological details reported by the identified studies (model based/ prospective study, type of economic evaluation undertaken)
- Summary of the reported cost-effectiveness of watch-and-wait strategy for rectal cancer.

Measures of effect

- Incremental costs
- Incremental consequences (measured using the method reported in the identified study)
- If appropriate, the summary measure combining incremental costs and consequences reported using the Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) of watch-and-wait strategy in comparison to resection surgery

Additional outcome(s)

None

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Identified studies from electronic search will be screened using three stage process. Identified studies will be exported to Mendeley which is a freely available reference manager. Any duplicate studies will be deleted and then the screening process will then begin. Titles and abstracts will be screened by two reviewers in parallel (ST and KP). A selection of full-text versions will then be screened and the final decision made to include the study in the review by three reviewers (ST, KP and AGR). Additionally, one reviewer (ST) will check the reference list of included studies to identify any potentially relevant studies. If there will be any discrepancies regarding the inclusion or exclusion of studies, it will be resolved through discussion with another reviewer (PT) from the team.

Data from included studies will be extracted using bespoke data extraction forms. Two separate data extraction tables will be created for: decision-analytic model-based economic evaluations and prospective economic evaluations. Information regarding study author, study population, intervention, comparator, study design, data on cost, result of economic analysis and sensitivity analysis will be recorded. Data extraction will be carried out by one reviewer (ST). Extraction accuracy will be checked by random sampling by two reviewers (LM and AGR).

Risk of bias (quality) assessment [1 change]

The Consolidated Health Economic Evaluation Reporting Standards 2022 (CHEERS 2022) will be used to critically appraise the quality of reporting for the identified economic evaluation. The checklist consist of 28-items and each included study will be assessed in terms of how the design met with the suggested criteria including the methodology referring to identification, measurement and valuation of costs and consequences, rationale for the selected study design, approaches to characterise uncertainty and reporting of the results.

One reviewer (ST) will do the quality assessment of the identified studies. A second reviewer (KP) will take a sample of 10% of the identified studies and do quality assessment independently. Then, two reviewers will meet and compare the results of quality assessment. If there is any disagreement, a third reviewer (PT) will be consulted to resolve the issue.

Strategy for data synthesis [1 change]

Narrative synthesis will be used with the goal of systematically assimilate the available economic evidence for watch-and-wait strategy. For this review, full economic evaluation (CEA, CUA and CBA) including prospective studies and decision-analytic model-based studies are included. Due to heterogeneity in these available types of study design (for example: model based studies using secondary data whereas prospective studies uses primary data) it is not possible to produce a quantitative synthesis of the results from the economic analysis. A qualitative summary of findings will be reported separately for model-based and prospective studies. Text and tables will be used to summarise study characteristics (population, intervention, comparator, identification, measurement and valuation of resources, type of cost included). The main result of the identified studies and sensitivity analysis will be presented in a summary table and a narrative summary of whether watch-and-wait strategy is cost-effective in comparison to resection surgery will be presented.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

Not applicable

Contact details for further information

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Review team members and their organisational affiliations [1 change]

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Type and method of review

Narrative synthesis, Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

01 March 2022

Anticipated completion date [1 change]

31 October 2022

Funding sources/sponsors

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Grant number(s)

State the funder, grant or award number and the date of award

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Conflicts of interest

Language

English

Country

England

Stage of review [1 change]

Review Completed not published

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

Chemoradiotherapy, Adjuvant; Humans; Neoadjuvant Therapy; Rectal Neoplasms

Date of registration in PROSPERO

24 February 2022

Date of first submission

16 February 2022

Stage of review at time of this submission [1 change]

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	Yes
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	Yes
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	Yes	Yes
Data extraction	Yes	Yes
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	Yes	Yes
Data analysis	Yes	Yes

Revision note

The review has been completed and preparation for manuscript has started.

The record owner confirms that the information they have supplied for this submission is accurate and complete and they understand that deliberate provision of inaccurate information or omission of data may be construed as scientific misconduct.

The record owner confirms that they will update the status of the review when it is completed and will add publication details in due course.

Versions

24 February 2022

19 January 2023